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Doses from ionising radiation in paediatric cardiac catheterisations in Norway 1975–2021

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Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Paediatric patients with congenital heart disease often undergo cardiac catheterisation procedures and are exposed to considerable ionising radiation early in life. This study aimed to develop a method for estimating the dose area product (P_{KA}) from paediatric cardiac catheterisation procedures (1975–1989) at a national centre for paediatric cardiology and to evaluate trends in P_{KA} and exposure parameters until 2021. Data from 2200 catheterisation procedures on 1685 patients (1975–1989) and 4184 procedures on 2139 patients (2000–2021) under 18 years of age were retrospectively collected. P_{KA} values were missing for 1975–1989 but available from 2000 onward. The missing P_{KA} was estimated from air kerma and beam area, based on exposure records and input from clinicians working at that time. P_{KA} trends were analysed over time and age. There was a 71% reduction in median P_{KA} from the period 1975–1989 (median 6.63 Gy cm²) to 2011–2021 (1.91 Gy cm²). The P_{KA} increases significantly ($p = 0.0001$) with patient age, which was associated with body weight. Approximately 80% of the total P_{KA} was from cine acquisition in 1975–1989, while 20% was from fluoroscopy. The P_{KA} estimate during 1975–1989 was considerably impacted by the assumptions of missing parameters such as tube filtration, focus-to-heart distance, beam area, and number of cine series. The decreasing trend in P_{KA} values was attributed to advancements in both technologies and clinical practices. The high contribution of cine acquisition to the total dose during 1975–1989 was due to factors such as a high frame rate, multiple acquisitions, and high tube current. The estimated P_{KA} values for the period 1975–1989 are of importance for the dose reconstruction and risk assessments in the EU epidemiology project Health Effects of Cardiac Fluoroscopy and Modern Radiotherapy in Pediatrics (HARMONIC).

1. Introduction

Children with congenital heart disease (CHD) are exposed to a substantial amount of ionising radiation through diagnosis, treatment and follow-up using radiological modalities including cardiac catheterisation, computed tomography and plain radiography [1–5]. The majority of the cumulative dose given to these patients comes from cardiac catheterisation [1, 3, 6–9]. Due to exposure to ionising radiation, paediatric patients are at increased risk of radiation-related late health effects since the sensitivity to radiation is higher in childhood compared to adulthood [1, 9–11]. Considering the long-term survival in CHD patients, the potential later health effects due to radiation exposure is a growing concern [12–17].

One main objective of the EU-funded multicentre study Health Effects of Cardiac Fluoroscopy and Modern Radiotherapy in Pediatrics (HARMONIC) (<https://harmonicproject.eu/>) (2019–2024) is to develop a European cohort of paediatric patients with CHD for long-term follow-up of radiation exposure and subsequent health outcomes. The project aims to provide estimates of radiation exposure in CHD children and associated risks of radiation-induced cancer [18, 19]. As part of the HARMONIC project, Norway identified a national cohort of paediatric patients with CHD and obtained information about cardiac catheterisation procedures from 1975 to 2021.

The two components of radiation exposure during cardiac catheterisation procedures are fluoroscopy and cine angiography [20]. The fluoroscopy mode, which is used for guiding the entire procedure and the cine acquisitions are used for both guiding the procedure and for documenting and storing images [21]. The number and length of digital acquisitions (cine) may be the greatest source of patient radiation dose in interventional cardiology procedures [22]. The general advice is to avoid cine angiography as much as possible to save radiation to the patients [23].

The standard method of reporting dose in interventional radiology is the reporting of dose area product (P_{KA}) [24]. HARMONIC aims to calculate conversion coefficients between P_{KA} values and organ doses using the new anthropomorphic paediatric and adult voxel phantom developed by the National Cancer Institute (NCI, US) and the dose calculator for Radiography and Fluoroscopy (NCIRF) [25, 26]. Catheterisation P_{KA} value is one of our deliveries to HARMONIC but, was not recorded by the equipment prior to 2000; thus, reconstructing organ doses from this era poses an additional challenge.

In Oslo University Hospital, P_{KA} for procedures in 1975–1989 is missing, and information about equipment and exposure settings is partly available. It is, therefore, challenging to reconstruct the doses for children exposed in the past, but it is very important as they are contributing data of utmost relevance in epidemiological analyses since they are followed up for long periods of time. However, a handwritten record of the procedures from 1975 to 1989 provides us with information about selective exposure parameters that might be useful to estimate the likely contribution from fluoroscopy and cine mode so that the HARMONIC's methods of translating P_{KA} to organ dose can be used. In addition, it is also important to explore the trend in P_{KA} to understand the expected impact of technological and clinical development over time supported by the principle of dose optimisation [27].

This study aims to develop a method to estimate the P_{KA} from cardiac catheterisations in paediatric patients with CHD treated between 1975 and 1989 based on assessments of air kerma and area at the position of the heart. We will also investigate possible trends in radiation dose and exposure parameters over time for cardiac catheterisation across three distinct periods: 1975–1989, 2000–2010, and 2011–2021. The P_{KA} estimated from this study can be used by the HARMONIC project to assess the correlation between organ doses and stochastic radiation effects [18, 19].

2. Methods

The research design is descriptive and received approval from the Norwegian Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (2019/335), with informed consent waived by the institutional data protection

officer. We are establishing a Norwegian cohort of paediatric CHD patients based on criteria defined collectively by the HARMONIC partners [1, 2], encompassing individuals who underwent at least one cardiac catheterisation, either diagnostic or interventional, before turning 18 years old. Patient data were sourced from the local registers at Department of Pediatric Cardiology, Oslo University Hospital, which holds a national role in paediatric cardiology [28].

The research was also observational and design was a retrospective case series, aimed to explore the trends in doses from catheterisations in the CHD patient cohort. Since most records detailing equipment characteristics and quality control were lost during the hospital's relocation in 2000, the study also involves method development. To reconstruct information about the equipment and parameters used during the catheterisations prior to 2000, we relied on personal communication with those retired paediatric cardiologists and radiologists who actually did the procedures, as well as manufacturers and physicists from the radiation protection authority who conducted inspections in the 1970s and 1980s (see acknowledgments).

2.1. X-ray equipment (1975–2021)

In the 1970s and 1980s, the hospital utilised an unspecified biplane x-ray system with over-couch geometry, likely Philips, equipped with image intensifiers and 35 mm film cameras, alongside a Tagarno viewer for reviewing cine acquisitions and no automatic exposure control (AEC) system. While specific equipment details remain unidentified, they likely resemble those described in old Norwegian teaching materials [29].

Information about equipment used in the 1990s could not be retrieved. The Siemens Coroskop T.O.P. with image intensifier was used from 2000 to 2010 and replaced in 2011 by the Siemens Axiom Artis Zee biplane with flat-panel detectors.

2.2. Materials and data sources

Numerous paper-based protocols outlining procedural parameters from 1975 to 1989 were located. We have documented 2200 catheterisation procedures performed during this period. Recorded information includes patient age, weight, sex, diagnosis and examination types. For cine acquisitions, parameters including tube voltage (kV), tube current (mA), cine frame rate (frame per second), exposure time (s) and projections were recorded. From the 1970s, fluoroscopy data included total fluoroscopy time (min), tube voltage (kV) and tube current (mA). However, only the fluoroscopy time was available from the 1980s. The use of total quantity of intravenous contrast administered (ml) was also available for each procedure. From 2000 to 2021, records of the procedures were retrieved from Radiology Information System (RIS). The information recorded included patient age, diagnosis, examination types, P_{KA} ($Gy\ cm^2$), and fluoroscopy time (min). Nearly 90% of examinations during 2000–2021 had total P_{KA} value recorded but, the cine and fluoroscopy contribution were not distinguishable. Picture Archiving and Communication System (PACS) data was collected to gather comprehensive information about cardiac catheterisation procedures. However, most of the radiation exposure parameters were missing for the years 2000–2010 and were primarily available only for cine acquisition from 2011 to 2021. An overview of equipment and available data over three time periods is given in table 1. From 2000 onward, patients were assigned a main diagnosis based on the International Paediatric and Congenital Cardiac Code and classified according to ICD-10 guidelines [30, 31]. Before 2000, multiple coding systems made consistent classification challenging. Diagnosis information is missing for 38% of patients (2000–2010) and 13% (2011–2021). Details are in table S1 of the supplementary material. There was no information about the use of grid for old equipment used prior to 2000. For the equipment used during 2000–2010 the grid was built in, and it was possible to remove for cases required. During 2011–2021, the grid was not recommended to be used for children weigh less than 20 kg.

2.3. The P_{KA} from catheterisation procedures

The P_{KA} is defined as the integral of the air kerma (K_{air}) over the x-ray beam area (A) in a plane perpendicular to the beam axis [32, 74]:

$$P_{KA} = \int_A K_{air} dA.$$

P_{KA} is currently either measured by a transmission chamber at the exit of the x-ray tube or calculated by the system [33]. In the approximation that the air kerma does not vary across the radiation field, P_{KA} is the product of the K_{air} and beam area [32]. The total P_{KA} for a whole catheterisation procedure adds up as a sum of all radiation events, i.e. all cine acquisitions and all use of fluoroscopy using the frontal and lateral planes.

2.4. Dosimetric reconstruction for procedures performed in 1975–1989

Data from 1970s and 1980s do not include any P_{KA} values measured or recorded for procedures. Therefore, K_{air} and beam area were estimated separately based on the parameters written on the record (table 1). For our estimate of P_{KA} , the heart was assumed to be placed in the isocentre of the imaging equipment.

2.4.1. Estimate of beam area at the centre of the heart

The cardiologists who performed the catheterisation in the 1970s and 1980s have confirmed that the x-ray beam was manually collimated to fit the heart. The area of the beam must take into account patient age, size, exposed body regions, and the specific projections used. The age-specific width and thickness of the chest (table S2 in supplementary material) were taken from a simplistic brick phantom (figure 1) designed by Persliden and Sandborg [34].

Projection is crucial in determining beam area. For cine acquisition, we observed three projections: anterior-posterior (AP), lateral (LAT), and oblique (without specific tube angulations). For fluoroscopy, in a biplane scenario with no information on projection, we have considered that approximately 70% of the exposure occurs in the AP projection and 30% in the LAT projection (Conversation with retired pediatric cardiologist and pediatric radiologist from Oslo University Hospital (Per G Bjørnstad and Bjarne Smevik 2023, oral communication, 14th February)). The heart is assumed to occupy 50% of the chest in AP and 67% in LAT projection (figure 2). Thus, the beam width was set to half of the phantom width in AP and two-thirds of the phantom thickness in LAT (figure 1). According to the cardiologist, the beam length accommodates part of the aorta and was set to about 1.5 times the width in AP projection (figure 2) (Sketch

by Per G Bjørnstad (Pediatric cardiologist, retired from Oslo University Hospital) in February 2023). In oblique projection, the heart was assumed to occupy the same area as in AP since the frontal tube was mostly angled to make oblique projections. The beam area at the level of the heart is calculated as follows,

$$A_{AP} = 0.5w_{\text{phantom}} \times 1.5 (0.5w_{\text{phantom}})$$

$$A_{LAT} = 0.67t_{\text{phantom}} \times 1.5 (0.5w_{\text{phantom}})$$

A_{AP} (cm^2) and A_{LAT} (cm^2) are the beam area at the level of the heart in AP and LAT projection, respectively, and w_{phantom} (cm) and t_{phantom} (cm) are the width and thickness of phantom, respectively.

2.4.2. Assessment of K_{air} at the level of the heart

The x-ray tube output, $Y(d)$ ($\mu\text{Gy mAs}^{-1}$ or mGy/mAmin), is defined as the $K_{\text{air}}(d)$ (μGy or mGy) at a specific focus detector distance, d , normalised to tube current-exposure time product (P_{It}) (mAs or mA min) [32]:

$$Y(d) = \frac{K_{\text{air}}(d)}{P_{\text{It}}}.$$

$Y(d)$ for various tube voltages, filtration and voltage form (table S3 in supplementary material) was provided in a teaching book for the x-ray tubes used in Norway in the 1970s and 80s [35]. For this study, we have assumed constant voltage (6 or 12 pulse ripple) and x-ray tube filtration of 3 mm Aluminium (Al). The 3 mm Al was also confirmed as the minimum filtration criteria of good radiographic technique suggested by the European Commission [36]. The air kerma for cine and fluoroscopy was calculated at the focus-to-isocenter distance (FID) considering that the heart is at isocenter and multiplied with the beam area to get the P_{KA} .

We conducted calculations based on the heart's position at the isocenter with the FID assumed as 75 cm. The K_{air} from cine acquisition is a sum of K_{air} from multiple series involved in imaging different regions of the heart. The cine exposure time per image (t_{event}) was 3 milliseconds and the cine frame rate (fps) was 75, but the total acquisition time was unknown. However, we know that cardiologists used cine film time (t_{film}) of 3 and 6 s for the left and right sides of the heart, respectively (Conversation with retired pediatric cardiologist and pediatric radiologist from Oslo University Hospital (Per G Bjørnstad and Bjarne Smevik 2023, oral communication, 14th February)), and we interpreted one film as one series, but we do not know how many films/series were used for one procedure. The cine air kerma per series was calculated by applying the inverse square law:

$$K_{\text{air,FID,cineseries}} = Y(d) \times \left(\frac{d}{\text{FID}}\right)^2 \times I \times t_{\text{event}} \times \text{fps} \times t_{\text{film}}$$

$$K_{\text{air,FID,cine}} = \sum_r (K_{\text{air,FID,cineseries}} \times N).$$

$K_{\text{air,FID,cineseries}}$ (mGy) and $K_{\text{air,FID,cine}}$ (mGy) are the air kerma at the level of the heart for a single cine series and for the total cine acquisition, respectively. I (mA) is the tube current, N is the number of film/cine series and r is the number of heart regions examined, e.g. ventricle, atrium, pulmonary, etc.

The total fluoroscopy time ($t_{\text{fluoroscopy}}$) is recorded in minutes for each procedure. The total air kerma is the sum of cine and fluoroscopy kerma at the level of the heart:

$$K_{\text{air,FID,fluoroscopy}} = Y(d) \times \left(\frac{d}{\text{FID}}\right)^2 \times I \times t_{\text{fluoroscopy}}$$

$$K_{\text{air}} = K_{\text{air,FID,cine}} + K_{\text{air,FID,fluoroscopy}}.$$

$K_{\text{air,FID,fluoroscopy}}$ (mGy) is the fluoroscopy air kerma.

2.4.3. Estimation of the number of cine series based on intravenous contrast media (IVC)

The written logs from 1975 to 1989 contain the amount of IVC used for each procedure. We assumed the total contrast volume was correlated to the number of cine series (cine film). The recommended standard dose of contrast for cardiac catheterisation, as suggested by Mullins [37], ranges from 1 to 5 ml kg^{-1} , with higher doses of up to 8 ml kg^{-1} considered. On the other hand, an old study by Fox *et al* [38] reported using 1.5–2 ml kg^{-1} body weight of ionic contrast in the 1970s and 1980s as safe. For this study, we have utilised a standard dose of 1.5 ml kg^{-1} of body weight contrast to determine the number of cine series (film), N :

$$N = \frac{\text{Total use of IVC per region examined (ml)}}{\text{Use of IVC per kg of body weight (ml/kg}^{-1}) \times \text{body weight (kg)}}.$$

2.4.4. Sensitivity analysis in the P_{KA} values from 1975 to 1989

Our estimate of P_{KA} is subject to substantial uncertainties due to four major missing parameters such as tube filtrations, FID, beam area and the number of cine series or film, which are mutually independent and directly or inversely proportional to the P_{KA} values. In addition to the estimated P_{KA} from the primary assumptions which are considered the most relevant, a possible range was determined by assessing scenarios with conservative and non-conservative assumptions of the missing parameters.

The $Y(d)$, provided by the Norwegian radiation protection authority in 1976 [35] largely varied with tube filtration. Every 1 mm increase in Al filtration causes a 40%–50% decrease in $Y(d)$ (table S3 in supplementary material), which subsequently impacts the P_{KA} . However, we miss information about the filtration in the data. Our primary assumption is 3 mm Al, but it could have been 2 mm with a non-conservative approach or 4 mm with a conservative approach.

The K_{air} at the heart is likely to vary with FID since K_{air} decreases with the square of the distance from the tube focus. We have calculated P_{KA} based on a typical FID of 75 cm. Though the actual FID for the old equipment with over-couch geometry was unknown, it was assumed to vary between 70 and 80 cm depending on the type of equipment [39–41]. Therefore, we have investigated the change in P_{KA} by varying FID to 70 cm (non-conservative) and 80 cm (conservative).

The beam area was not known but estimated from paediatric phantom (figure 1) for different projections and relies on the assumption of how the size of the heart occupies the trunk of the phantom, and the presumption that the cardiologists collimated to the heart (figure 2). However, the estimated beam areas are found to be 20%–40% bigger than the heart area measured from real patient CT data in different ages (table S4 in supplementary material). Therefore, we looked into changes in P_{KA} due to variations in beam area: 20% more (non-conservative) or 20% less (conservative).

We also did not know the exact number of cine series used in each procedure, but an estimate can be made based on the use of IVC. According to Fox *et al* [38], the safe practice for IVC use starts from 1.5 ml kg⁻¹ of body weight. This was our primary assumption for the number of cine series calculations. However, we also investigated the impact of using 1 ml kg⁻¹ or 2 ml kg⁻¹ of IVC. The number of cine series was higher with 1 ml kg⁻¹ IVC. Therefore, this amount was considered non-conservative. Conversely, 2 ml kg⁻¹ IVC decreases the number of cine series. Hence, it was considered a conservative amount.

2.5. Collection of PACS data 2000–2021

PACS data were collected through a custom software called DICOMInspector (Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology [LIST], Luxembourg), which was developed for use in HARMONIC. The software generates an exportable Excel file. The data file provides necessary exposure parameters arranged in an instance, series, and study along with the study date, description, and patient's age, sex, and weight. During 2000–2010, most of the exposure parameters, such as tube voltage, current, cine rate, exposure time, filtration, and P_{KA} , are missing. These parameters have been consistently reported from 2011 onward.

2.6. Trend in P_{KA} and exposure settings

The trends in P_{KA} , fluoroscopy time and exposure parameters (kV, mA) are presented over six age groups and three time periods: 1975–1989, 2000–2010 and 2011–2021, categorised by the use of three different equipment. The P_{KA} values presented for 1975–1989 are those measured with the primary assumptions of related parameters.

2.7. Statistical analysis

The distribution of P_{KA} , kV, mA, fluoroscopy time and use of contrast were estimated across six age categories based on the patient's age at the time of examination: 0–3 months, 4–30 months, 31–90 months, 91–150 months, 151–210 months and 211–216 months. This corresponds to HARMONIC's age groups: newborn, 1 year, 5 years, 10 years, 15 years, and adult (late adolescent), respectively [13]. The p values are measured with a nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis rank test. All data analyses were conducted using Stata version 17 (StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX).

3. Results

The number of patients and procedures with age-stratified median weights from different time periods and sources are presented in table 1. Approximately 20% (453 out of 2200) of procedures conducted during 1975–1989 lacked recorded any exposure parameters and were consequently excluded from the calculation of P_{KA} . Roughly 50% (2024 out of 4184) of procedures from the RIS were retrieved from the PACS, with the latter primarily storing the cine component of the procedures. Procedures conducted during 1975–1989 were predominantly diagnostic (5.3% interventional). From early 2000, more interventional procedures started to be performed and mostly combined with diagnostic parts. There were patients receiving more than one procedure, and the results showed that the catheterisation procedures were performed in all age groups. The weights of paediatric patients in the age category of 211–216 months closely resemble those of adult patients in certain instances.

DICOM digital imaging and communications in medicine, FID focus to isocenter distance, fps frame per second, IQR inter quartile range, IVC intravenous contrast, K_{air} kerma in air, m months, N number of cine

Table 1. Overview of equipment, data sources and available information used in dose reconstruction in three periods of development in one hospital with national responsibilities for paediatric cardiac patients in Norway (data from the 1990s are missing).

Time period	Equipment	Data Sources	Procedure type	Parameters available	Missing data for dose reconstruction	Number of patients	Number of procedures	Number of procedures with recorded P_{KA} values	Dose reconstruction parameters available							
									Patients	Procedures	0–3 m	4–30 m	31–90 m	91–150 m	151–210 m	211–216 m
1st (1975–1989)	Philips scanner, with image intensifiers and 35 mm film cameras	Paper based record	Interventional and Diagnostic	Demographic: Patient age, weight and sex Cine: kV, mA, fps, t_{event} and IVC amount Fluoroscopy: $t_{fluoroscopy}$ and kV and mA (only from 1970s)	K_{air} , FID, beam area, t_{film} , N , P_{KA}	1685	2200	None	1367	1747	3.5 (3, 3.9)	7.5 (5.6, 9.6)	16.8 (14, 20.1)	28 (24, 33.3)	51 (40, 58)	61 (56.6, 66.3)
2nd (2000–2010)	Siemens Coroskop T.O.P. with image intensifier	RIS & PACS	Interventional and diagnostic	Total P_{KA} from RIS	DICOM metadata from PACS	1298	2299	1956	None	None	4.4 (3.6, 5.2)	10 (7.8, 11.4)	15.6 (13.4, 18.5)	31.3 (24.4, 38)	56 (42, 65)	—
3rd (2011–2021)	Siemens Axiom Artis Zee biplane with flat-panel detectors	RIS & PACS	Interventional and diagnostic	Total P_{KA} from RIS and DICOM metadata for cine acquisition from PACS	Exposure data for fluoroscopy	1063	1885	1829	869	1345	4.1 (3.2, 5.1)	9.1 (7.3, 11.4)	16 (14, 18)	31 (25.8, 37.5)	55 (44.5, 63)	64.3 (58.2, 73.4)

Table 2. Detail of cine and fluoroscopy dose area product (P_{KA}) distribution over six age categories during 1975–1989 assuming 3 mm Al filtration, 75 cm focus to isocenter distance (FID), beam area collimated to the heart in AP and LAT projection, 1.5 ml kg⁻¹ intravenous contrast (IVC).

Age category	Exposure	P_{KA} (Gy cm ²)			
		Mean (SD)	Median (IQR)	Min	Max
0–3 months	Cine	2.56(1.65)	2.31(1.29–3.35)	0.13	14.13
	Fluoroscopy	0.61(0.56)	0.45(0.29–0.7)	0.06	4.37
	Total	3.14(1.89)	2.85(1.68–4.18)	0.14	17.29
4–30 months	Cine	5.15(3.39)	4.58(2.82–6.54)	0.35	26.22
	Fluoroscopy	1.01(0.86)	0.76(0.48–1.24)	0.07	7.97
	Total	6.03(3.72)	5.3(3.57–7.8)	0.14	29.1
31–90 months	Cine	7.68(4.68)	6.67(4.25–10.01)	1.04	28.08
	Fluoroscopy	2.27(2.49)	1.5(0.99–2.71)	0.17	27.12
	Total	9.72(5.73)	8.29(5.69–12.66)	0.21	36.12
91–150 months	Cine	10.53(7.04)	8.92(5.6–13.8)	0.91	43.24
	Fluoroscopy	4.07(3.25)	2.97(1.85–5.31)	0.41	18.79
	Total	14.1(8.86)	12.06(8.14–18.24)	0.42	53.73
151–210 months	Cine	18.46(12.36)	15.79(9.79–23.53)	2.82	55.82
	Fluoroscopy	11.07(13.3)	6.95(3.78–13.89)	0.5	111.99
	Total	29.21(20.22)	23.03(15.61–39.1)	6	139.69
211–216 months	Cine	16.81(3.3)	16.41(13.73–20.3)	13.73	20.3
	Fluoroscopy	6.52(2.46)	5.59(4.66–9.31)	4.66	9.31
	Total	23.33(3.5)	24.96(19.32–25.72)	19.32	25.72
Total (all age combined)	Cine	7.21(6.88)	5.22(2.91–9.12)	0.13	55.82
	Fluoroscopy	2.54(5.02)	1.17(0.56–2.57)	0.06	111.99
	Total	9.55(10.2)	6.63(3.76–11.77)	0.14	139.69

IQR inter quartile range, SD standard deviation.

series or film, PACS picture archiving and communication system, P_{KA} dose area product, RIS radiology information system, t_{film} duration of one cine film, $t_{\text{fluoroscopy}}$ fluoroscopy time, t_{event} exposure time per image.

3.1. Dose values from 1975–1989

The P_{KA} values per procedure between 1975 and 1989, categorised by fluoroscopy and cine acquisition and stratified by age groups, are presented in table 2. Nearly 80% of total P_{KA} was from cine acquisition and 20% from fluoroscopy. Cine contribution tends to be higher for older age groups (figure 3).

3.2. Sensitivity assessment in P_{KA} due to missing parameters in 1975–1989

The impact of variations in related factors on P_{KA} estimation is presented in tables 3 and 4. Across all age groups, P_{KA} 's highest deviation (~40%) is from ± 1 mm change in Al filtration, and the lowest was from ± 5 cm change in FID (table 4). The estimated P_{KA} may vary by up to a factor of two, depending on whether parameters were selected conservatively or non-conservatively.

3.3. Dose trend from 1975 to 2021

The P_{KA} was associated with the age of the patient. P_{KA} values significantly decreased ($p = 0.0001$) over time (table 5). Overall, there was a 71% dose reduction from the period 1975–1989 to 2011–2021. Total fluoroscopy time per examination also varied significantly ($p = 0.0001$) across time periods (table 5), with the highest range observed in 2000–2010.

3.4. Trend in cine tube voltage and current (1975–2021)

This study examined the trend of cine tube voltage and current over age and time, presenting data from 1975–1989 and 2011–2021 (figure 4). Both tube voltage and current showed significant changes over age ($p = 0.0001$) but the magnitude of current is not directly comparable between these two time periods since in 2011–2021 it was pulsed and in 1975–1989 it was continuous. Median voltage increased by approximately 25% in patients with ages >150 months from 1975–1989 to 2011–2021 (figure 4(a)). Moreover, during 2011–2021, there has been a notable increase in the current level for patients aged >90 months (figure 4(b)).

Figure 3. Cine and fluoroscopy contribution to the median dose area product (P_{KA}) per procedure in 1975–1989 across different age categories assuming 3 mm Al filtration, 75 cm focus to isocenter distance (FID), beam area collimated to the heart in AP and LAT projection, 1.5 ml kg^{-1} intravenous contrast (IVC).

4. Discussion

In this study, we proposed a method to estimate P_{KA} for cardiac catheterisation procedures conducted in paediatric CHD patients between 1975 and 1989 and describe the P_{KA} together with other exposure parameters over three periods (1975–1989, 2000–2010, 2011–2021). Due to limited available information during 1975–1989, we relied on expert input and personal communication with retired cardiologists, radiologists, and physicists to reconstruct P_{KA} . We aggregated data from 2200 catheterisation procedures in 1685 patients during 1975–1989, and 4184 procedures in 2139 patients during 2000–2021. For the former period, P_{KA} values were estimated for 1747 procedures based on available exposure parameters (kV, mA, frame rate, exposure time, fluoroscopy time and projection), while for the latter period, 3785 procedures had recorded P_{KA} values (table 1). Our analysis revealed that from 1975 to 1989, cine acquisition had the major contribution, accounting for nearly 80% of the total P_{KA} . Compared to fluoroscopy, higher cine P_{KA} was primarily due to the high cine frame rate, multiple acquisitions, and high tube current. The P_{KA} estimation was subject to considerable uncertainties due to missing parameters (tube filtration, FID, beam area, and the number of cine series). With our primary assumption of 3 mm Al tube filtration, 75 cm FID, beam area collimated to the heart in AP and LAT direction and number of cine series using 1.5 ml kg^{-1} body weight of IVC, the median P_{KA} per procedure ranges 2.85–24.96 Gy cm² across different ages. However, the P_{KA} can be up to two times larger or smaller compared to the primary estimation, based on the selection of the factors non-conservative and conservative, respectively. We investigated the trend in P_{KA} , dividing the timeline into three periods due to the introduction of new and improved equipment and procedures. Over three time periods we observed a decreasing trend in the P_{KA} , which can be attributed to the adoption of modern equipment with improved dose control protocols and recommendations for dose optimisation supported by published dose reference levels for paediatric cardiac interventional procedures [24, 42–47, 75].

4.1. Cine contribution to the total P_{KA} in 1975–1989

In this study, the cine contribution (80% [70%–86% across different age groups]) to the total estimated P_{KA} for procedures in 1975–1989 was higher than the contribution from fluoroscopy (table 2), which is, however, justified by Hirshfeld *et al* [48] stating that the radiation dose per frame for cine acquisitions can be up to 15 times greater than for fluoroscopy. This finding is in accordance with a contemporary study by Leung and Martin [35], reporting 68% P_{KA} contribution from cine acquisition with a frame rate of 12.5–25 fps for the patient group, similar to our 211–216 months. Rowley [49] reported that the cine exposure contribution to the total exposure was around 68%, with 200 fps, and 51%, with 100 fps, on 0–13 years patients. On the contrary, the majority of the studies conducted on the paediatric population during the 1970s and 80s reported relatively lower cine doses (with up to 64 fps) than fluoroscopy [50–52]. A study by Leibovic *et al* further found differences in cine contribution to the total exposure in LAT (52%–59%) and PA (29%–35%) projections. In our study, the high cine dose (figure 3) in 1975–1989 was primarily due to the high cine frame

Table 3. Impact of variations in related factors on dose area product (P_{Ka}) estimate.

Fixed factors	Median P _{Ka} (IQR) (Gy cm ²)						
	FID, beam area and number of cine series	Beam area, tube filtration and number of cine series	FID, tube filtration and number of cine series	FID, beam area and tube filtration	FID, beam area and tube filtration	None	
Variable factors	Tube filtration	FID	Beam area	Number of cine series	All	All	
Age categories	2 mm Al (non-conservative) ^a	70 cm (non-conservative)	20% more area (non-conservative)	20% less area (conservative)	Number of cine series with 1 ml kg ⁻¹ IVC (non-conservative)	Number of cine series with 2 ml kg ⁻¹ IVC (conservative)	All factors non-conservative ^b All factors conservative ^c
0–3 m	2.85(1.68–4.18)	3.27(1.92–4.82)	3.41(2.01–5.02)	2.28(1.35–3.37)	3.19(1.95–4.78)	2.44(1.56–3.64)	6.76(4.21–10.13)
4–30 m	5.3(3.57–7.8)	6.1(4.1–8.95)	6.37(4.29–9.36)	4.24(2.85–6.24)	6.09(4.15–8.97)	4.48(2.95–6.44)	12.95(8.72–18.72)
31–90 m	8.29(5.69–12.66)	9.52(6.54–14.53)	9.95(6.83–15.19)	6.63(4.56–10.13)	10.76(7.42–15.35)	7.71(5.41–11.5)	22.4(15.69–31.97)
91–150 m	12.06(8.14–18.24)	13.84(9.35–20.94)	14.47(9.77–21.89)	9.65(6.51–14.59)	15.28(9.8–22.08)	11.9(8.08–17.83)	31.33(20.23–45.13)
151–210 m	23.03(15.61–39.1)	26.45(17.92–44.88)	27.65(18.74–46.91)	18.43(12.49–31.28)	24.38(16.25–40.8)	23.03(15.61–39.1)	50.73(33.23–84.43)
211–216 m	24.96(19.32–25.72)	28.64(22.18–29.53)	29.94(23.17–30.87)	19.96(15.45–20.58)	24.96(19.32–25.72)	24.96(19.32–25.72)	50.08(40.78–54.8)
Total	6.63(3.76–11.77)	7.62(4.3–13.51)	7.96(4.5–14.13)	5.3(3–9.41)	8.03(4.32–13.93)	5.97(3.29–10.59)	16.78(9.07–29.08)

^a Primary assumption of missing parameters: 3 mm Al filtration, 75 cm FID, area collimated to the heart and number of cine series using 1.5 ml kg⁻¹ IVC.

^b All factors non-conservative: 2 mm Al filtration, 70 cm FID, 20% more area than the primary assumption and number of cine series using 1 ml kg⁻¹ IVC.

^c All factors conservative: 4 mm Al filtration, 80 cm FID, 20% less area than the primary assumption and number of cine series using 2 ml kg⁻¹ IVC.

FID focus to isocenter distance, IQR inter quartile range, IVC intravenous contrast.

Table 4. Percentage of deviation in dose area product (P_{KA}) estimation due to variation in related factors.

Age categories	Deviation in P_{KA} (%)			
	± 1 mm filtration	± 5 cm FID	$\pm 20\%$ beam area	± 0.5 ml kg ⁻¹ IVC
0–3 m	42.5	13.4	19.9	13.2
4–30 m	40.0	13.5	20.1	15.1
31–90 m	38.0	13.5	20.0	18.4
91–150 m	37.7	13.5	20.0	14.0
151–210 m	35.2	13.5	20.0	2.9
211–216 m	35.1	13.4	20.0	0.0
Total	39.7	13.5	20.1	15.5

FID focus to isocenter distance, IVC intravenous contrast.

rate (75 fps). Multiple acquisitions (1–7 cine series per procedure) in different projections might also trigger the dose. In addition, the tube current for cine acquisition was substantially higher than fluoroscopy. Data for 2000–2021 does not provide the P_{KA} value separately for fluoroscopy and cine acquisition; therefore, we could not present their individual contribution in total P_{KA} . However, studies conducted during this time period, such as Tsapaki *et al* [42], reported that 49% of total P_{KA} comes from cine acquisition with 12.5–50 fps for diagnostic catheterisation procedures on patients aged ≤ 17 years. Rizk *et al* [53] reported 32%–37% cine contribution to total P_{KA} with 30 fps for ≤ 16 years. This means that a lower frame rate can potentially reduce the cine dose but it is also important to use the cine more sparingly to reduce the overall dose for a procedure [54].

4.2. Impact of missing parameters in 1975–1989

Unlike modern integrated equipment, machines from 1975–1989 were assembled from parts by different manufacturers according to need and demand. Personal communication revealed that there were likely changes in parts over these years, but detailed information was lacking. As a result, specific equipment details like tube filtration and FID were missing. Operators manually selected exposure parameters, as there was no AEC. For projections other than AP and LAT, patients were positioned using pillows, and the angles were often not recorded.

Several factors primarily contribute to the uncertainties in P_{KA} estimates from 1975 to 1989. For example, tube filtration might have varied (2 mm, 3 mm, or 4 mm), and each mm change can significantly impact tube output (table S3 in supplementary material) and consequentially causes nearly 39% deviation in P_{KA} (table 3). We assumed 3 mm Al tube filtration, aligning with European Commission recommendations [36] and contemporary studies [55, 56]. However, using 4 mm Al could substantially reduce the dose, as noted by Behrman [57]. The primary assumption of 75 cm FID was based on equipment specifications of different manufacturers, but this is often ranges from 70 to 80 cm. This study report about 13% P_{KA} deviation from a ± 5 cm change in FID.

We were uncertain about collimation practices from 1975 to 1989. Our estimated beam area for the frontal tube matches recent measurements from structured dose track data of 245 patients (table S4 in Supplementary Material), but the lateral tube area shows a large difference, likely due to stricter collimation in LAT projection during 1975–1989. However, we have estimated nearly 20% deviation in P_{KA} from $\pm 20\%$ change in beam area due to collimation. The use of contrast per unit body weight during this period was also unclear, though ionic x-ray contrast was a concern for infants and children undergoing cardiac catheterisation [58]. We took a conservative approach in estimating cine series from contrast use (≤ 2.0 ml kg⁻¹), supported by Fox *et al* [38]. Our study however reports nearly 15% deviation in P_{KA} for a ± 0.5 ml kg⁻¹ change from the primary assumption of 1.5 ml kg⁻¹.

Despite these uncertainties, our estimated P_{KA} can be used in epidemiological studies. In HARMONIC, uncertainties will be assessed using the 2DMC approach [59, 60], producing multiple realisations of potential true doses from input parameters' probability density functions. Our data can serve as input for the 2DMC analysis.

4.3. Trend addressing technical and clinical development

During the years 1975–1989, procedures were mostly diagnostic. Interventional procedures began to be more frequent in the late 1990s (Conversation with retired pediatric cardiologist and pediatric radiologist from Oslo University Hospital (Per G Bjørnstad and Bjarne Smevik 2023, oral communication, 14th February)). Therefore, dose values from 2000 to 2021 are from all procedures combined. Typically diagnostic procedures involve lower doses compared to interventional ones [8, 17, 35, 36, 54, 75]. Yet doses in 1975–1989 were

Table 5. Range of dose area product (P_{KA}) and fluoroscopy time per procedure across different time periods and age categories.

Age categories	Median P_{KA} (IQR) ($Gy\ cm^2$)				$P\ value^a$	Median fluoroscopy time (IQR) (min)				$P\ value^a$
	1975–1989	2000–2010	2011–2021			1975–1989	2000–2010	2011–2021		
0–3 m	2.85(1.68–4.18)	2.39(1.29–3.83)	0.72(0.45–1.54)		0.0001	14 (10, 22.5)	18.8 (11.8, 34.8)	13 (5.9, 21.9)		0.0001
4–30 m	5.3(3.57–7.8)	3.28(2.01–5.25)	0.88(0.52–1.49)		0.0001	13 (9, 20)	16.8 (10, 28.4)	10 (6, 17.23)		0.0001
31–90 m	8.29(5.69–12.66)	4.74(2.45–8.1)	1.52(0.71–2.76)		0.0001	10 (6.5, 16.5)	16.2 (9, 30)	11 (7, 18.1)		0.0001
91–150 m	12.06(8.14–18.24)	9.75(4.89–19.04)	2.64(1.16–7.06)		0.0001	11 (7, 17)	18.05 (9.9, 31.4)	8.93 (6, 14)		0.0001
151–210 m	23.03(15.61–39.1)	19.66(9.06–38.69)	9.26(3.92–23.22)		0.0001	13 (8, 25)	14.67 (6.8, 29.9)	9 (6, 15)		0.0001
211–216 m	24.96(19.32–25.72)	31.68(4.6–32.49)	28.07(11.43–61.05)		0.5714	9 (7.5, 15)	6.9 (6.3, 32)	15.4 (10.6, 19)		0.6442
Total	6.63(3.76–11.77)	4.16(2.2–8.59)	1.91(0.79–5.83)		0.0001	12 (8, 19.5)	16.6 (9.8, 30.2)	10 (6, 16.9)		0.0001

^a P values indicate significant differences among time periods according to the Kruskal–Wallis rank test. IQR inter quartile range.

Figure 4. Cine tube voltage (kV) (a) and current (mA) (b) across different age categories and time periods.

significantly larger than in 2000–2021 (table 5). However, there was about a 54% dose reduction from 2000–2010 to 2011–2021, which resulted from the replacement of Siemens Coroskop T.O.P. (image intensifier) with the Siemens Axiom Artis Zee (flat panel detector) expected to be more efficient in dose reduction, as supported by Nickoloff [61]. However, such dose reduction was primarily attributed to continuous clinical and technical development with more focus on dose optimisation aided with improved equipment design and AEC which particularly ensure the use of spectral beam filtration, higher x-ray beam energy, and limited fluoroscopy and acquisition pulse rates suggested by earlier studies [62–64, 76, 77]. The use of virtual collimation, last image hold, storage of fluoroscopy, limiting fluoroscopy time and minimising high dose modes such as high contrast mode are also proven to be sufficiently reducing the dose [65]. Similar to our findings, Wassef *et al* [66] has observed a 48% decrease in radiation by adjusting the technical settings of x-ray equipment and implementing dose reduction protocols. Moreover, significant dose reduction in paediatric cardiac catheterisation has been achieved over the past couple of decades through the implementation of weight or age-specific dose reference levels [75, 78, 79] and by staff education, training and awareness to minimise exposure during interventional procedures [67, 68].

Like P_{KA} , fluoroscopy time is typically shorter for diagnostic than therapeutic procedures [8, 17, 35, 36, 54, 62]. Therefore, from 2000, when the procedures started encompassing more therapeutic segments with diagnostic, the fluoroscopy time increased as expected (table 5). However, since 2011, a significant fall has been observed, which underscores the impact of modern equipment and dose-reduction strategies.

The study of trend in exposure parameters was only limited to cine tube voltage and current as these two parameters were available in data from 1975–1989 and 2011–2021. Typically, kV and mA both increase with patient age, mainly due to the thickness of the patient, which was observed in both periods (figure 4). The observed kV and mA outliers were mainly due to a wide spread of weight as well as thickness within each age group. For the old equipment (1975–1989), the kV and mA were manually chosen based on the expected image quality and did not vary a lot for a particular weight range. Whereas, in modern equipment (2011–2021), kV and mA are the AEC parameters determined by a specific protocol (fluoroscopy or acquisition) and fluctuate within a pre-determined range to adjust image quality and exposure to the patients. Generally, to save dose for very small patients, the machine starts with the lowest possible kV and mA, but if more dose to the detector is needed, it ramps up the kV and stabilises it at a certain point, and then ramps up the mA. Often the added Copper filtration is used instead of increasing kV. The added Copper filtration also influences the current. Usually, the machine runs with high mA when there is more filtration. In this study, the rise of mA for >90 months patients in 2011–2021 (figure 4(b)) is likely due to increased added filtration while keeping kV nominal.

4.4. Dose value comparison with literature

Few studies from the 1970s and 1980s reported P_{KA} values for paediatric catheterisation procedures. Rowley [49] reported a range of 1.2–15.5 Gy cm², and Leibovic and Fellows [52] reported 4.1–9.5 Gy cm² for

patients aged 0–13 years, similar to our findings (table 5) for ages 0–150 months from 1975 to 1989. Rassow *et al* [69], covering 1984–1996, reported a median P_{KA} of 5–20 Gy cm² for patients under 21 years, aligning with our findings (2.85–24.96 Gy cm²) for patients under 18 years. Although doses are not directly comparable due to differences in procedures, equipment and techniques, it strengthens our method by validating the dose range. In this study, for the period 2000–2010, the median P_{KA} for all procedures combined (table 5) across six paediatric age groups is comparable to the median P_{KA} of 0.5–36.9 Gy cm² reported by Harbron *et al* [70] for similar age groups across three hospitals, even though this study includes few procedures not performed at our hospital. For the period 2011–2021, we found the lowest median P_{KA} (table 5) across all age groups, which is in a similar range to the values reported by Barnaoui *et al* [71] (0.7–12.8 Gy cm²) and Rizk *et al* [53] (0.5–20 Gy cm²) for procedures similar to ours.

4.5. Study limitations

Dose reconstruction for 1975–1989 is subject to uncertainties due to missing parameters, particularly regarding procedural settings, geometry, and projection (table 1). We developed our method based on qualified assumptions and personal communication with retired hospital staff. Due to the lack of contemporary literature, we could not validate all this information. Additionally, the use of a brick phantom (figure 1) to estimate children's dimensions may introduce uncertainties in dose calculation for the individuals in the cohort. Beam area depends on projection and collimation varying with patients and procedures, but since we relied solely on sketches from cardiologists (figure 2) for heart collimation in AP and LAT projections, our calculation of beam area might obviously deviate from the actual beam area. Other missing factors such as tube filtration, FID, and IVC per kg body weight further contribute to the uncertainty in the estimated P_{KA} value, which we estimated using both conservative and non-conservative approaches. From 2000 onward, we had combined interventional and diagnostic procedures, as well as cine and fluoroscopy dose values, preventing us from separately reporting their individual contributions. Furthermore, we also did not have concrete information about use of grid but the recent recommendations [72] advise not to use the grid for smaller patients. We assume in 70s and 80s they might already did not use the grid for smaller patients. However, the impact of the grid on the dose can be big but this is accounted for in the DAP or mA that were collected as well as calculated [73].

5. Conclusion

This national study was conducted as part of HARMONIC project to provide the estimate of P_{KA} values for the cardiac catheterisation procedures conducted during 1975–1989 to facilitate better dose reconstruction and risk estimate for CHD patients with early exposure to ionising radiation. We have also explored the trend in P_{KA} over three time intervals (1975–1989, 2000–2010, 2011–2021) with major shifts in technology followed by exploring trends in tube voltage and current available for two periods (1975–1989, 2011–2021). The P_{KA} for the procedures in 1975–1989 was based on the estimate of air kerma and beam area separately that involves some qualified assumptions for the missing parameters such as filtration, FID, beam area and use of IVC per unit body weight. We have observed that a major portion of P_{KA} resulted from cine acquisition rather than fluoroscopy due to the high frame rate, multiple acquisitions, and high tube current during 1975–1989. However, the estimated P_{KA} from this period is subject to uncertainties due to missing parameters. The sensitivity analysis indicates that the estimated P_{KA} may vary by up to a factor of two, depending on whether parameters are selected conservatively or non-conservatively. The significant decreasing trend found in P_{KA} over three time periods primarily resulted from the technology shift with improved equipment, procedures and dose control protocols. International recommendations for dose optimisation supported by published dose reference levels, along with growing awareness among clinicians contributed to dose optimisation for paediatric cardiac interventional procedures. The findings of this study will help HARMONIC to assess uncertainties with sophisticated methods by accounting for possible missing parameters and help clinicians understand the benefit of technical advancement and optimisation.

Data availability statement

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are not publicly available because the data is primarily collected for project HARMONIC. According to Norwegian legislation, our approvals to use the data for the current study do not allow us to distribute or make the data directly available to other parties.

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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Conflict of interest

The authors of this manuscript declare no relationships with any companies, whose products or services may be related to the subject matter of the article.

Ethical approval

The project was approved by regional committees for medical and health research ethics in Norway in April 2019 (2019/335). A Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) was approved by the data protection officer in November 2020. Since then, the project has developed with changes regarding staff and methods. Therefore, a revised project protocol was approved in March 2023. Accordingly, a revised DPIA is to be approved. All data management and analyses were conducted on data with no individual person identification. All results are distributed on a group level, without any possibilities for individual identification. All data management and analyses were conducted on data with no individual person identified. The identification key is stored and governed by the Oslo University Hospital.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Data collection was performed by (Utheya Salini Thevathas) and (Margrethe Meo). Material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by (Susmita Afroz), (Hilde M Olerud) and (Bjørn Helge Østerås). The first draft of the manuscript was written by (Susmita Afroz) and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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